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Style and design

The term style is commonly associated with high art.¹ One popular use of it refers to artistic movements, like the various *isms* of twentieth century art. These movements often passionately advocate the exploration of special themes and the use of certain techniques. Another frequent use of 'style' emphasizes marks of authorship, the manifestation of the artist's individuality in a work of art: 'a real Picasso'. The more artists are able to express these marks consistently in their entire oeuvre, and the more complex the oeuvre is, the higher their work is appreciated by many. Style in these two examples tells us more about the alleged psychological make-up of the artist, e.g. an Adlerian need for recognition, than that it clarifies qualities of the art work or its resemblance to other works. Let alone that it sheds light on the emotional experience that art works provoke, the subject of this paper. Fortunately, there is a definition of style that 1) does touch on similarities that one art work shares with another and 2) does relate the artist's intent to the art work's specific qualities. Leonard Meyer's (1989, p.3) definition in his work on style in music emphasizes an abstract patterning that one particular art work shares with another. Closely following Meyer, style, be it defined for schools, oeuvres or individual works, is *a characteristic pattern in the choice of techniques made within some set of constraints*. The choice is not necessarily a deliberate one, and the constraints may arise from a number of different sources, e.g. historical convention specific to an art form or genre, the availability of technological means and contemporary ideology and tastes. Crucial to the definition is the idea that art works are what they are by virtue of the fact that they could have been otherwise. Choice of a particular technique means that there were other options. Especially Ernst Gombrich's (1960) studies on the history and psychology of art have documented the idea of style as *problem solving*. The artist tries out solutions to problems of form, and solutions are as Meyer proposes, a patterned use of techniques within certain constraints.

It has been observed by Gombrich (1980) as well as by others that artists' intentions and the formal problems they attempt to solve have changed from one period to another and differ from one region to another (See also Cutting and Massironi, 1998). For instance, Renaissance artists sought to represent three-

¹ For an overview of uses of the concept of style see Lang (1987).

dimensional space as an observer would see it in the real world, in order to serve as the stage for events and figures with a precise spiritual significance. Baroque artists focused on the expression of matter and texture and the intricate way that light alters their looks. If we sufficiently widen the time and space frames of artistic production, including for instance Egyptian art and so-called applied and folk arts, the variety of goals that artists set themselves or that are being set to them, as well as the diversity of means and contextual limitations becomes so large, that the specific high-art connotation that the term style has, gives way to the more general label *design*. Widening the definition given by Meyer and Gombrich, to include functional consumer products, we define *design* as the pattern of characteristic choices recognisable in an artefact, made within certain constraints, including the main function of the artefact.

Style and emotion

Elsewhere (Tan, in press) I have argued that art works provoke two kinds of emotion. One has the represented world as its object. Depending on what is central in this world, e.g. persons, events, action, scenes, etc. R(epresented world)-emotions include fear, pity, sadness, astonishment, joy, and so on. The other kind of emotion has the work of art as a man-made artifact as its object. Desire, admiration, surprise, interest and enjoyment are examples.

We assume that style in the arts contributes to emotion in the recipient in two ways. First, it may boost, filter, or modify R-feelings that originate in the subject or theme that is represented. A vampire is horrifying by itself, a defeat provokes pity and shame, etc., whether met in real life or in a painting or short story. Style can render a represented vampire less aversive, or stress its horrific looks. Second, style may itself be a primary source of A- emotion. We may be fascinated by Bach's inventive variations on a theme, or be pleased when discovering the consistency in Cézanne's transformation of shapes.

Awareness of style and emotion

When style acts as an amplifier or modifier of R-emotion, it does not have to be consciously perceived by the recipient. It does its work unnoticed. However, few recipients will be as naïve as to never observe strategies, techniques or procedures chosen by the artist. In fact, strong A-emotion produced by such illusionist works as Hollywood films leave ample room for the least sophisticated viewer to enjoy the director's mastery of the trade. Who would not

marvel Alfred Hitchcock's cunning tactics in maximising suspense and fear in his audience? On the other hand, giving too much thought to the challenge that the artist has set him or herself and possible alternative solutions would keep the recipient from attending to the represented world. So we can ask ourselves how awareness of style influences the recipients' emotional experience of the art work. More in particular it would be worth the while to know whether and how experts' feelings compare to aesthetic emotion in untrained recipients. Do they watch more distantly at events in the fictional world, searching for stylistic novelties?

Some empirical findings

In previous research, these questions have been addressed with some success. I cannot give a complete overview here. When we limit the discussion to liking or evaluation as the major A-affect, we can mention an experiment by Cupchik & Gebotys (1988), who found that untrained recipients prefer traditional figurative paintings over abstract ones. Hekkert and van Wieringen (1990a) found that untrained viewers' liking was based more on recognisability of represented content, whereas value judgements of experts are related to typicality of style (Hekkert and van Wieringen, 1990b).

In our own research on cinematic expertise, we had observed that sophisticated viewers, those who visit art houses, read serious film magazines slightly but consistently empathize less with figures in the film. We have attempted to establish whether there is a mode of aesthetic viewing that weakens R emotion, a distant way of viewing, searching for stylistic novelty. We

reasoned that there may be a more direct measure of knowledge and appreciation of style than sophistication.

In a pilot study, we developed a measure of cinephilia, that is the degree to which film viewers are sensitive to style, and have knowledge of, attend to and recognise deviations from the most canonical film style. (Tan, Eggermont, and Joosten, 1989). The measure correlates with interest in art at large, but it predicts preference for high art films better than other measures of cultural training and participation.

In a first study on emotion in high vs. low cinephiliacs Tan, Eggermont, Joosten and Spinhof viewers watched

a moderately popular film, *Once upon a time in the West* (S. Leone, 1969). The film is an atypical Western because the viewer has to guess until the final scene what the hero wants from the antagonist. Style is used to leave uncertainty about his past. In flash backs we see only fragments of some traumatic event, but only fragments that are shot out of focus. The following variables were included:

1. R-emotion: feelings for the protagonists, e.g. pity and admiration during selected scenes
2. Perception of style: complexity, ambiguity, narration, genre, tempo
3. A-emotion: appreciation, valuation, of film and style
4. Cinephilia as a stable trait

High-cinephiliacs gave the film a higher appreciation mark and found it more valuable.² In addition they rated it as less complex than low-cinephiliacs.

Cinephiliacs enjoyed complexity and ambiguity.

For instance, they appreciated the fact that the reason why the Harmonica man (Bronson) has his revenge on Frank (Fonda) is only explained at the very end of the film. They also liked the extreme low tempo in some scenes, and the play with the Western style. On the other hand, the hero's autonomy and the victory of justice that he brings about, was enjoyed more by low- than by high

cinephiliacs, as was the closed ending of the film. High cinephiliacs felt less pity for the McBain family when they were shot. In spite of these differences, high cinephiliacs agreed with low-cinephiliacs in the majority of measured emotions. The results seem to support a distant viewing hypothesis, that is they suggest that viewers with knowledge of film style in general and a preference for art style in particular may have stronger A-emotion, and especially feelings based on recognition of original twists to more common uses of narrative procedures. They may have weaker R-emotions, especially those caused by the protagonist's fate. In line with this, it was found in this study and in the pilot that cinephiliacs are less interested in genre movies that are characterized by one dominant set of emotions, such as the comedy, romance and action films.

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A second study (Andringa, Tan, van Horssen and Jacobs, in press) threw more light on the question whether cinephiliacs watch in a more distant fashion, by asking viewers for their empathy while watching the film (state empathy), and empathy in daily life. They watched Peter Delpeut's *Emma Zunz* (1984), after Borges' short story. Emma lives a lonely and empty life as a factory girl. She has been left by her father when she was five years old.

² A stepwise multiple regression analysis showed that cinephilia was the best predictor of the appreciation mark from a set including film habits (frequency, magazines, art houses), interest in art, and education.

He used to work as a cashier in the same factory where Emma is working. He now lives in a far-off country. One day she receives word that he has killed himself, and this is where the film starts, omitting Emma's history. The plot remains highly ambiguous up to the final sequence, where Emma kills her boss. Like *Once upon a time* the film conceals what Emma wants until the end. Only then it becomes clear that her father had had to flee after being falsely accused by the boss of a theft. But in this film most of the time we even do not understand anything of her character and thoughts, or even what she is doing. We see her arrange and clean things, and burn letters, and it all seems pointless. Her face is concealed from viewing, and dialogue is almost absent. By the end of the film we can, in retrospect, understand that since she received the fatal letter, she has been meticulously planning and preparing the shooting of the boss. There is not much room for R-emotion, except some feeling of uneasiness watching Emma's seemingly meaningless life. The film's style, then, is characterized by a Bresson-like restricted narration, including repetitive staging and camera set-up. The manipulations consisted of adding information to the film that enabled viewers to empathize more with Emma. In one condition, a short summary was given before the film started, including the information about the events that preceded the plot. In two others, voice-over comments were added that revealed Emma's past soon after the start of the film. One voice-over was a first-person narration, the other a third- person narration. The following measures were taken:

1. R-emotion: feelings for the protagonists, e.g. pity and admiration
2. Empathy while watching
3. A-emotion: interest, appreciation, admiration for film maker, irritation
4. Cinephilia as a stable trait
5. Empathy as a stable trait

The results were surprising, in that R-emotions, especially feelings for the protagonist, such as pity and sympathy were not affected by adding more information about the meaning of events to Emma. But A-emotions were, with a clear trend towards a diminishing aesthetic appreciation for the film and its maker when information about the represented world was added. However, high-cinephiliacs appreciated the film better than low-cinephiliacs in the information condition, in the original and voice over conditions there was no difference between the two groups. High cinephiliacs showed higher levels of interest while viewing, they found the film more beautiful, and less irritating, and admired the director more than low-cinephiliacs. Also, A-emotion of high cinephiliacs in the information condition was highest of all over conditions and groups. Empathy as a personality trait was not correlated with cinephilia but it was with R-emotion. Empathy as a trait was also correlated with A-emotion, and interestingly, empathy while watching the film, that is a concern for Emma Zunz, was much more strongly related to A-emotions, appreciation and enjoyment of beauty than cinephilia.³

The results of this experiment can be interpreted to

³ When corrected for cinephilia, positive empathy correlated still significantly with A-emotions, while correcting for empathy rendered the correlation of cinephila with A-emotion insignificant.

mean that the film's lack of communicating what happens in the represented world is compensated for by filling in feelings and thoughts that the protagonist may have. That is why viewers who strongly empathize appreciate the film better than low empathizers. However, although cinephiliacs are as empathetic as anyone else in life, they can empathize more than others if the film calls for and enables active imagination. For them, imaginative empathy is part of the positive A-emotion. In this particular case, when no information was given, they needed a hint; the film did not by itself afford their imaginative participation.⁴ The summary of the plot helped them to bring their skills into play, and to recognize that the film systematically denies access to Emma's inner world, and how it does this. Recognizing the film's style, the difficulty that the film maker sets for himself in the first place, and then for the viewer, helps in enjoying the film. However, when more information is added from outside, the film loses its aesthetic appeal. Its challenge to the viewer's empathic imagination is given away like in *Once upon a Time*. High empathizers may, when not cinephiliac, also engage in filling in what the film leaves out, because they can use their general skill or propensity.

Taken together the two studies suggest that the ability to perceive style may be used to control R-emotion, the more or less naïve response to fictional events, but does not necessarily imply a coldly observing mode of reception. It just depends on what the art work invites the beholders to do, and what their preferred skills are. Viewers who understand what the film does, how it does what it does, and why, can readily see what to do themselves. I owe to M. Csikszentmihalyi the idea that the required response should meet the person's capacities, that is, be not too difficult, but certainly not too easy (Csikszentmihalyi & Csikszentmihalyi, 1988). Those are exactly the conditions of a positive A-emotion: an awareness of a choice of techniques by the film maker that anticipates use of some favourite skill on the part of the beholder.

Emotion caused by style as design

The problem solving approach to artistic style contains a deep parallel with design in a more general sense. Design is the solution to a problem posed by a product's main functions, and the limitations posed to its production and use. An industrially manufactured piece of furniture has to offer value for money as an object that you can sit on, store your things in, and so on. It has to be cost effective in producing, and users may have additional wishes to satisfy, such as economy of space and durability. If a product meets all the

⁴ It may be that viewers with higher cinephilia scores than the cinephilacs in our psychology freshman sample would be able to empathize.

producing, and users may have additional wishes to satisfy, such as economy of space and durability. If a product meets all the

requirements, the only emotion it will provoke in the user is satisfaction, and perhaps enthusiasm. We can compare the man or woman sitting on the chair or using the CD rack to the viewers of popular movies, who laugh and weep, according to the genre they have ordered and paid for, and feel good. The `design' of the movie is taken for granted, it is not perceived, it does not `show through' the product. But recognition of the product's design as design is needed, that is a recognition of the problem or challenge that the designers have set themselves, if the user is to have an aesthetic emotion. I can see at least three conditions met by some industrially designed products which provoke recognition and admiration for their design:

- economy: combine various functions in a new way, save duplication of functions. A famous example is the map of the London underground system, that succeeds in representing all the lines and their connections in one small and still readable picture, by a complicated transformation of the one-to-one projected distances.
- anticipation of user capacities and limitations. Examples include products for special user categories, e.g. handicapped, inhabitants of third-world countries, but also some 'advanced options' in a graphic modelling software package.
- beauty: the design attracts attention to itself, because of a particular use of technique, stylization, expressive qualities and the like. The latter condition may be called aesthetic in the usual art-related sense. For its recognition it is most dependent on knowledge of previous products and schools of design. Products that conform to it are the ones that fill design departments of art museums, and here design can be completely identical to style in the artistic sense, depending on the importance of the products main function. I am certain that there are more conditions leading to A-emotion than I have listed here. They may be combined, as when Philippe Starck would design a new water bottle that shows possible contamination of its contents and would be fit for reuse. What they all may have in common is the visibility of intentional problem solving on the part of the designer.

Concluding remarks

Both artistic style and design cannot be recognised without knowledge. The user of a product has to be aware of the aims the designer had in mind in order to appreciate the design at all. Furthermore, knowledge of the available techniques and technology may help finer appraisals of value in design. Finally, prevailing likes and dislikes will codetermine any A-emotion in the user. It seems obvious that there are lovers of design, just as we have shown the existence of cinephiles, who not only are more knowledgeable of and sensitive to design,

but also may have strongly developed aficionado tastes for certain designers and schools. It is important that research in design is extended to cover questions like these:

- how much knowledge of production, use, and limiting context factors is necessary in order to appreciate the design of a product, and how much knowledge of comparable examples?
 - what role do existing preferences play in liking for design?
 - what knowledge and what kind of aesthetic sensitivity is involved in enjoying purely aesthetic or formal characteristics of designed products?
- The study of emotion and style in art and that of emotion provoked by design share an interest in such questions, and we can only hope that they will join forces in exchanging data and insights of mutual interest.

Appendix Selected items of Cinephilia test

Items consisted of statements. Respondents had to indicate their agreement on a five point scale ranging from 'completely disagree' to 'completely agree'.

- Some films constantly give you the feeling that you are watching a movie, because you do'nt get a grip. That can be fascinating.
- There should be a clear theme in a film story, e.g. the chase of a criminal, a romance, a feud, or an adventure.
- I feel disturbed if a film clearly reveals that it is all acted, and that what you see is not real.
- If it is unclear in a film where and when events are set, this can have arresting effects.

A film story can be limited to one and the same space, for instance one room. That is not necessarily a drawback.

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